

Synthesis and fluorescence behaviour of star-shaped pyridine and benzene cored stilbenoid compounds

Debabrata Jana and Binay Krishna Ghorai*

Department of Chemistry, Bengal Engineering and Science University, Shibpur, Howrah-711 103,
West Bengal, India

E-mail : bkggorai@yahoo.co.in Fax : 91-33-26682916

Manuscript received 27 January 2011, accepted 20 June 2011

Abstract : Three-branched pyridine and benzene cored stilbenoid compounds were synthesized utilizing multifold Heck coupling reaction. A preliminary study of the optical properties of the resulting compounds was conducted by UV and fluorescence spectroscopy.

Keywords : Stilbenoid compounds, three-fold Heck reaction, fluorescence.

Introduction

In recent years, star-shaped three-arm conjugated molecules with high photoluminescence efficiencies have been extensively studied because of their interesting electrical, optical and optoelectronic properties¹⁻¹⁴. Moreover, they are model compounds for the corresponding polymers. Particularly, substituted pyridine-based stars have been claimed as electroluminescent materials¹⁵, two photon absorbing dyes¹⁶⁻¹⁸, and they also form mesophases^{19,20} which is important for one-dimensional conducting systems. Many pyridine-cored star-shaped conjugated oligomers with a large variety of additional substituents on central and peripheral rings as well as conjugated π -system have been explored in the past. However, only a few star-shaped compounds with a large stilbene peripheral unit have been reported in the literature. Generally, acid or base (Siegrist reaction) catalyzed condensation reactions have been used for the synthesis of stars with pyridine core. We decided to use the Heck arylation reaction to construct all the stilbenoid linkages (both at the core and in the periphery) of our oligomers which provides a *trans* selective synthetic route to stilbenoid compounds. Recently synthesis and optical properties of pyridine-cored first-generation V-shaped dendrimers bearing phenylenevinylene oligomeric branches in periphery has been reported²¹. This paper focuses on the synthesis and studies of the optical absorption and emission properties of new pyridine/benzene-cored three-branched stilbenoid compounds.

Results and discussion

Requisite 1-vinyl(4-*tert*-butylstyrene)benzene (**1**)²² required for our study, was synthesized from the readily available methyl 4-bromobenzoate (**2**) in good yield as outlined in Scheme 1. At first, Heck reaction on **2** with 4-*t*-butylstyrene under Jeffery's conditions²³ provided the ester **3** (76%) and subsequent treatment of **3** with lithium aluminium hydride in THF gave the alcohol **4** (79%) and the later was oxidized (PDC, CH₂Cl₂, rt) to produce the styrylbenzaldehyde **5** (86%). Wittig reaction of **5** (Ph₃P⁺MeI⁻, *n*-BuLi, THF) at -20 °C afforded vinylstyrene derivative **1** in 72% yield.

Generally, multifold Heck coupling reaction for stilbenoid compound's preparation afforded low yields due to the insolubility of partially coupled intermediates, which were observed to precipitate from solution during early reaction times²². We have chosen 2,4,6-tribromopyridine as a core molecule to prepare stilbenoid compound because it has a π -acceptor property. This controls the absorption and emission spectra and also the nitrogen atom of pyridine ring enhances the solubility of the mono- and bis-coupled products, which lead to the complete conversions with a considerable easy isolation and purification process. For comparative study, we have used 1,3,5-tribromobenzene as a core molecule.

Core molecule 2,4,6-tribromopyridine (**6**) was readily prepared from 2,6-dibromopyridine in a good yield following the literature procedure described by Shetty *et al.*²⁴. Stilbenoid compound **8** was synthesized utilizing

Scheme 1. Reagents and conditions : (a) 4-*t*-Butyl styrene, Pd(OAc)₂, *n*-Bu₄NBr, KOAc, DMF, 90 °C; (b) LiAlH₄, THF, rt; (c) PDC, CH₂Cl₂, rt; (d) Ph₃P⁺MeI⁻, *n*-BuLi, THF, -20 °C.

three-fold Heck reaction of **6** with 4-*tert*-butylvinylstyrene under Jeffery's phase transfer conditions [10% Pd(OAc)₂, *n*-Bu₄NBr, KOAc, DMF, 90 °C] in 25% yield (Scheme

2). Under the same conditions, Heck reaction of 2,4,6-tribromobenzene (**7**) with same periphery led to the benzene-cored stilbenoid compound **9** in 22% yields.

Scheme 2. Synthesis of stilbenoid compounds. Reagents and conditions : (a) 4-*t*-Butylstyrene (3.5 equiv.), Pd(OAc)₂, *n*-Bu₄NBr, KOAc, PPh₃, DMF, 90 °C, 24 h; (b) **1** (3.5 equiv.), Pd(OAc)₂, P(*o*-tolyl)₃, Et₃N, DMF, 100 °C, 48 h.

For preparation of stilbenoid compounds **10** and **11** bearing vinylstyrene as a peripheral unit, we followed the coupling reaction procedure as described by Bazan *et al.*²². Coupling with **6** afforded strongly fluorescent three branched compound **10** in 20% yield. The coupling reaction with **7** under the same condition resulted in a three branched compound **11** in 15% yield. For long chain coupling reactions, more time was required and yields were also much less.

The optical properties of the stilbenoid compounds were investigated by UV and PL spectroscopy on CH₂Cl₂ solutions of the compounds at room temperature. Fig. 1 and Fig. 2 shows the UV spectra and photoluminescence spectra of compounds **8** and **9** respectively, the main data obtained are listed in Table 1.

Fig. 1. Absorption (solid line) at $C = 1.01 \times 10^{-5} M$ and emission spectrum (dotted line) of **8** at $C = 1.02 \times 10^{-7} M$.

Fig. 2. Absorption (solid line) at $C = 1.2 \times 10^{-5} M$ and emission spectrum (dotted line) of **9** at $C = 1.2 \times 10^{-6} M$.

Table 1. Spectroscopic data of stilbenoid compounds **8-11**

Comps.	UV	Excitation	Fluorescence ^a
	λ_{\max} (nm)	λ_{\max} (nm)	λ_{\max} (nm)
8	316	316	420
9	318	318	394
10	342, 352	352	449
11	360	360	405, 424

^aNormalized fluorescence spectra were taken in dichloromethane.

For compounds **8** (Fig. 1) and **9** (Fig. 2) maximum absorption wavelengths are in the UV region (318 nm). The peaks at 318–320 nm were assigned to the particularly for the stilbene units. The absorption peak at the region 350–360 nm for the compound **10**, this is due to the peripheral distyrylbenzene. The important feature of 1,3,5-trisubstituted benzenes with conjugated arms is their *meta* substitution pattern. *meta* Substitution is known to prevent the conjugation between the individual arms of the star-molecules in their ground state. The same type of variation in absorption phenomenon due to the change of the core molecule (Table 1) is observed.

The photoluminescence (PL) spectral data (Table 1) shows the considerable amount of change in emission wavelength with increasing π -conjugation in the *para*-position. For example, the PL spectra of compound **10** shows strong red shift with a λ_{\max} of 449 nm than that of compound **8** with a λ_{\max} of 420 nm. If we compare the PL spectra of benzene-cored system with the pyridine-cored system, interestingly, the maximum emission peak for both **8** and **10** are red shifted with respect to **9** and **11** respectively (*ca.* 26 nm for **8** and *ca.* 44 nm for **10**). The emission behavior of pyridine ring star is different with respect to benzene homologue this is due to pyridine ring has a electron-withdrawing character, significant aromaticity that can lead to highly conjugated molecules, as well as basic and potential ligand properties. Fluorescence quantum yields of **8** and **9** are 0.12 and 0.22²⁵.

In conclusion, we have successfully synthesized and characterized new 2,4,6-tri(arylvinyl)pyridine derivatives by three-fold Heck coupling reaction between 2,4,6-tribromopyridine or 2,4,6-tribromobenzene and appropriate vinylphenylene moiety. From the comparative study of photoluminescence behaviors it is concluded that pyridine-cored stilbenoid compounds emit in higher λ_{\max} re-

gion than that of benzene cored analogues. Detailed work in this area is currently underway in this laboratory.

Experimental

All melting points are uncorrected. IR spectra were recorded on a Jasco FT/IR-460 plus instrument (KBr or neat). The ^1H NMR and ^{13}C NMR spectra were recorded at Bruker-DPX 300. LCMS spectra were recorded on an Agilent 6120 mass spectrometer. MALDI-MS were recorded on an Applied Biosystems 4700 Proteomics Analyzer 170. Splitting patterns of ^1H NMR spectra are designated as s, singlet; d, doublet; t, triplet; q, quartet; m, multiplet; br, broad. Unless otherwise noted, all reactions were carried out under an inert atmosphere in flame dried flasks. Solvents and reagents were dried and purified by distillation before use as follows: tetrahydrofuran and diethyl ether from sodium benzophenone ketyl; dichloromethane and chloroform from P_2O_5 ; DMF and diisopropylamine from CaH_2 ; pyridine from solid KOH. After drying, organic extracts were evaporated under reduced pressure and the residue was column chromatographed on silica gel (Spectrochem, particle size 100–200 mesh), using an ethyl acetate-petroleum ether (60–80 °C) mixture as eluent unless specified otherwise.

Synthesis of methyl 4-(2-(4-tert-butylphenyl)vinyl)benzoate (3) :

A mixture of dried KOAc (1.9 g, 19.5 mmol), *n*-Bu₄NBr (6.27 g, 19.4 mmol), DMF (10 mL) were stirred for 15 min in a double necked round-bottomed flask in argon atmosphere at room temperature. To the reaction mixture **2** (3 g, 9.74 mmol), PPh₃ (765 mg, 2.9 mmol), 4-*tert*-butylstyrene (2.15 mL, 11.68 mmol) were added simultaneously and again stirred for 15 min. Catalytic amount of Pd(OAc)₂ was added and heated for 24 h at 90 °C. The mixture was cooled to room temperature and extracted with hexane and ether mixture (1 : 1) (30 mL). The organic layer was washed with distilled water (3 × 25 mL), brine solution and then dried (anhydrous Na₂SO₄). Solvent was removed in a rotary evaporator. Purification by column chromatography using hexane as eluent afforded **3** (1.83 g, 61% yield). IR (KBr, cm⁻¹) : 2953, 1717, 1598, 1434; ^1H NMR (500 MHz, CDCl₃) δ : 7.48 (4H, m), 7.40 (4H, m), 7.20 (1H, d, *J* 16.3 Hz), 7.08 (1H, d *J* 16.3 Hz), 3.91 (3H, s), 1.34 (9H, s); ^{13}C NMR

(125 MHz, CDCl₃) δ : 166.9, 151.5, 142.1, 132.8, 131.1, 130.0, 126.8, 126.5, 126.2, 125.7, 52.0, 34.7, 31.2.

Synthesis of 4-(2-(4-tert-butylphenyl)vinyl)phenyl)methanol (4) :

To a suspension of LiAlH₄ (42 mg, 1.1 mmol) in dry THF (5 mL) a solution of **3** (1.0 g, 3.2 mmol) was added dropwise at 0 °C under argon atmosphere. The reaction mixture was stirred for 36 h at room temperature. Aqueous solution of saturated sodium sulphate (3 mL) was added to the reaction mixture to decompose excess LiAlH₄. The mixture was extracted with EtOAc (2 × 10 mL). Combined organic layer was dried over anhydrous Na₂SO₄. Solvent was removed in a rotary evaporator. Purification by column chromatography using hexane and ethyl acetate (1 : 1) gave the desired product **4** (645 mg, 65% yield). ^1H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl₃) δ : 7.47 (4H, m), 7.35 (4H, m), 7.08 (2H, s), 4.67 (2H, s), 1.33 (9H, s); ^{13}C NMR (75 MHz, CDCl₃) δ : 150.7, 139.9, 136.9, 134.4, 128.4, 127.3, 126.5, 126.2, 125.5, 65.01, 34.5, 31.2.

Synthesis of 4-(2-(4-tert-butylphenyl)vinyl)benzaldehyde (5) :

A solution of **4** (500 mg, 1.8 mmol) in dichloromethane (5 mL) was added dropwise to the red solution of CrO₃·2Py [prepared from vigorously stirred suspension of CrO₃ (1.9 mmol) and pyridine (3.8 mmol) in dry CH₂Cl₂ (5 mL) for 1.5 h at room temperature] at 0 °C and stirred for 2 h at the same temperature. The mixture was then diluted with Et₂O (10 mL) and passed through a bed of silica gel (5 g). The solution was then concentrated under reduced pressure and purified by silica gel column chromatography (EtOAc-petroleum ether, 3 : 1) to give **5** (255 mg, 51% yield). The spectral data was identical to that reported¹.

Synthesis of 4-tert-butylstyrene-1-vinylbenzene (1) :

To a solution of triphenylmethylphosphonium bromide salt (714 mg, 2.0 mmol) in THF (8 mL), *n*-BuLi (1.6 M) (1.1 mL, 1.8 mmol) was added dropwise at -20 °C under N₂ atmosphere. The mixture was stirred for 1 h at -20 °C and allowed to attain room temperature. A solution of **5** (500 mg, 1.8 mmol) in dry THF (1 mL) was added to the reaction mixture and stirred for 3 h at room temperature. The reaction mixture was quenched with water (0.5 mL).

The mixture was extracted with ether (3 × 10 mL) and dried over anhydrous Na₂SO₄. Solvent was removed in a rotary evaporator. Purification by column chromatography using hexane as eluent afforded compound **1** (245 mg, 48% yield). The spectral data was identical to that reported¹.

*Palladium-catalyzed coupling reaction of 4-*t*-butylstyrene with tribromobenzene/pyridine analogue : a typical procedure for the multiple Heck coupling reaction :*

A mixture of dried KOAc (90 mg, 0.92 mmol), *n*-Bu₄NBr (296 mg, 0.92 mmol) in DMF (6 mL) was stirred for 15 min in a double necked round-bottomed flask under argon atmosphere at room temperature. 2,4,6-Tribromobenzene (**6**) (100 mg, 0.30 mmol), PPh₃ (3 mg, 0.01 mmol) and 4-*tert*-butylstyrene (172 mg, 1.07 mmol) were added simultaneously to the reaction mixture. Mixture was stirred for another 15 min. Catalytic amount of Pd(OAc)₂ was added and heated at 90 °C for 24 h. The mixture was cooled to room temperature and extracted with hexane and ether mixture (1 : 1) (2 × 20 mL). The organic layer was washed with water (2 × 5 mL), brine (5 mL) and dried over anhydrous Na₂SO₄. Solvent was removed in a rotary evaporator and the crude product was purified using column chromatography (silica gel/ ethyl acetate : petroleum ether 1 : 99) to yield the compound **8** (41 mg, 25%).

Compound **8** : IR (KBr, cm⁻¹) : 2957, 1636, 1575, 1557; ¹H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl₃) δ : 7.71 (2H, d, *J* 16.2 Hz), 7.57 (4H, d, *J* 8.1 Hz), 7.52 (2H, d, *J* 8.1 Hz), 7.42 (6H, d, *J* 7.8 Hz), 7.35 (2H, s), 7.21 (2H, d, *J* 16.5 Hz), 7.03 (2H, d, *J* 16.2 Hz), 1.35 (27H, s); LC-MS (*m/z*) 554.5 (M⁺).

Compound **9** : Compound **9** was prepared from 2,4,6-tribromobenzene (0.30 mmol) using the procedure described for the preparation of compound **8**. Yield : 36 mg (22%); m.p. 91 °C; IR (KBr, cm⁻¹) : 3025, 2959, 1584, 1511, 1462; ¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ : 7.53 (3H, s), 7.49 (6H, d, *J* 8.0 Hz), 7.40 (6H, d, *J* 8.0 Hz), 7.22 (3H, d, *J* 16.2 Hz), 7.11 (3H, d, *J* 16.3 Hz), 1.34 (27H, s); ¹³C NMR (125 MHz, CDCl₃) δ : 150.9, 138.2, 134.5, 129.0, 127.7, 126.3, 125.7, 123.6, 34.7, 31.3; HR-MS : *m/z* [M]⁺ Calcd. for C₄₂H₄₈ : 552.3756; Found : 552.3758.

Palladium-catalyzed coupling reaction of 1 with tribromobenzene/pyridine analogue : a typical procedure for the multiple Heck coupling reaction :

A mixture of dried triethylamine (2 mL), tribromoanalogue (6.31 mmol) and styrene derivative **1** (172 mg, 1.07 mmol) in DMF (6 mL) were stirred for 15 min in a double necked round-bottomed flask at room temperature under argon atmosphere. To the reaction mixture catalytic amount of Pd(OAc)₂ and tris(*o*-tolyl)phosphine (5 mg, 0.016 mmol) was added and heated for 48 h at 100 °C. The mixture was cooled to room temperature and extracted with chloroform (2 × 15 mL). The organic layer were washed with water (3 × 5 mL), brine (5 mL) and dried over anhydrous Na₂SO₄. Solvent was removed in a rotary evaporator and the crude product was purified using column chromatography (silica gel/ ethyl acetate : petroleum ether 1 : 99) to yield the compounds **10** and **11**.

Compound **10** : Yield : 53 mg (20%); IR (KBr, cm⁻¹) : 2924, 2852, 1597, 1270; ¹H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl₃) δ : 7.60–7.53 (11H, m), 7.52–7.37 (18H, m), 7.20 (4H, d, *J* 16.0 Hz), 7.13 (1H, d, *J* 8.0 Hz), 7.07 (4H, d, *J* 16.0 Hz), 1.34 (27H, s); MS (MALDI-TOF) (*m/z*) 860.0 [M+H]⁺.

Compound **11** : Yield : 39 mg (15%); IR (KBr, cm⁻¹) : 2960, 1516, 1411, 1117; ¹H NMR (500 MHz, CDCl₃) δ : 7.58–7.48 (12H, m), 7.46 (3H, s), 7.43–7.33 (12H, m), 7.18–7.08 (12H, m), 1.34 (27H, s); MS (MALDI-TOF) (*m/z*) 858.2 [M+H]⁺.

Acknowledgement

This work is supported by UGC [No. 37-93/2009 (SR)], UGC-SAP and CSIR (Research Fellowship to DJ), New Delhi, Government of India.

References

1. H. Detert, M. Lehmann and H. Meier, *Materials*, 2010, 3, 3218.
2. A. L. Kanibolotsky, I. F. Perepichkaz and P. J. Skabara, *Chem. Soc. Rev.*, 2010, 39, 2695.
3. S. Kim, H. Kalbitz, S. Hillmann and H. Meier, *Eur. J. Org. Chem.*, 2009, 1976.
4. S. Jamaguchi, T. Shirazaka and K. Tamao, *Org. Lett.*, 2000, 2, 4129.
5. A. Bhaskar, G. Ramakrishna, Z. Lu, R. Twieg, J. M. Hales,

- D. J. Hagan, E. Van Stryland and T. Goodson III, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 2006, **128**, 11840.
6. Y. Yamaguchi, T. Ochi, S. Miyamura, T. Tanaka, S. Kobayashi, T. Wakamiya, Y. Matsubara and Z. Yoshida, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 2006, **128**, 4504.
 7. Y. H. Kiang, G. B. Gardner, S. Lee, Z. Xu and E. B. Lobkovsky, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1999, **121**, 8204.
 8. H. Meier, *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed.*, 1992, **31**, 1399.
 9. I. Jung, T. Lee, S. O. Kang and J. Ko, *Synthesis*, 2005, 986.
 10. M. Lehmann, B. Schartel, M. Hennecke and H. Meier, *Tetrahedron*, 1999, **55**, 13377.
 11. H. Meier, M. Lehmann, H. C. Holst and D. Schwöppe, *Tetrahedron*, 2004, **60**, 6881.
 12. D. W. Chang and L. Dai, *J. Mater. Chem.*, 2007, **17**, 364.
 13. S. Eisler, N. Chahal and R. McDonald, *Chem. Eur. J.*, 2003, **9**, 2542.
 14. P. Roy, D. Jana and B. K. Ghorai, *Bull. Chem. Soc. Jpn.*, 2010, **83**, 1269.
 15. S. Shigeo, S. Shimizu and H. Takano, JKXXAF JP 07285937 A19951031, 1995; CAN 124:175851.
 16. H. Wang, Z. Li, P. Shao, Y. Liang, H. Wang, J. Qin and Q. Gong, *New J. Chem.*, 2005, **29**, 792.
 17. M. Matsui, S. Kawamura, K. Shibata and H. Muramatsu, *Bull. Chem. Soc. Jpn.*, 1992, **65**, 71.
 18. A. Abbotto, L. Beverina, R. Bozio, A. Facchetti, C. Ferrante, G. A. Pagani, G. Pedron and R. Signorini, *Chem. Commun.*, 2003, 2144.
 19. T. Lifka, A. Oehlhof and H. Meier, *J. Heterocycl. Chem.*, 2008, **45**, 935.
 20. A.-J. Attias, C. Cavalli, B. Donnio, D. Guillon, P. Hapiot and J. Malthête, *Chem. Mater.*, 2002, **14**, 375.
 21. D. Jana and B. K. Ghorai, *Lett. Org. Chem.*, 2010, **7**, 203.
 22. S. Wang, W. J. Oldham (Jr.), R. A. Hudack (Jr.) and G. C. Bazan, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 2000, **122**, 5695.
 23. T. Jeffery, "Advances in Metal-Organic Chemistry", JAI Press, Greenwich Publishers, 1996, Vol. 5, pp. 153.
 24. R. Shetty, D. Nguyen, D. Flubacher, F. Ruggle, A. Schumacher, M. Kelly and E. Michelotti, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 2007, **48**, 113.
 25. Quantum yields were measured in CH₂Cl₂ solutions using pyrene ($\Phi = 0.32$ in cyclohexane) as standard (errors within 15%).